

Capture and Storage of Carbon Dioxide

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Abstract: In response to climate change and its adverse effects, 197 countries adopted the Paris Agreement at the 21st Conference of the Parties in Paris on December 12, 2015, recognizing the importance of limiting the rise in global temperature. This goal necessitates reducing the impact of greenhouse gases, primarily from human activities, which includes the crucial task of removing accumulated gases from the Earth's atmosphere. Our study explores the imperative of capturing and storing carbon dioxide (CO₂) to limit the global temperature increase to approximately two degrees Celsius. This requires the extraction of a round 600 gigatons of CO₂ during this century, translating to the annual disposal and safe storage of tens of gigatons of CO₂. We investigate various methods and techniques for CO₂ removal, both natural and industrial, with the aim of reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels to those at the onset of the industrial revolution (approximately 280 parts per million). The study proposes and evaluates several methods, some of which are currently in use, to assess their effectiveness and impact on the planet's ecosystem. This includes a thorough consideration of their applicability, material costs, and feasibility, as well as the long-term effects of large-scale decarbonization. One significant method examined is the storage of CO₂ in geological layers, oceans, and minerals, offering innovative insights into these techniques as viable solutions for large-scale CO₂ reduction.

Keywords: Carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS), Carbon capture, Climate Change, Paris Agreement, Carbon leak, Decarbonization, Carbon Storage.

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Introduction

Introduction and framework of this study Carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS), the subject of this study, is considered as one of the options for reducing atmospheric emissions of CO₂ from human activities. The purpose of this Special Report is to assess the current state of knowledge regarding the technical, scientific, environmental, economic, and social dimensions of CCS and to place CCS in the context of other options in the portfolio of potential climate change mitigation measures. The structure of this technical study follows that of the Special study. This introductory section presents the general framework for the assessment together with a brief overview of CCS systems. Section 2 then describes the major sources of CO₂; a step needed to assess the feasibility of CCS on a global scale. Technological options for CO₂ capture are then discussed in Section 3, while Section 4 focuses on methods of CO₂ transport. Following this, each of the storage options is addressed. Section 5 focuses on geological storage, Section 6 on ocean storage, and Section 7 on mineral carbonation and industrial uses of CO₂. The overall costs and economic potential of CCS is then discussed in Section 8, followed by an examination in Section 9 of the Implications of CCS for greenhouse gas emissions inventories and accounting. The Technical Summary concludes

with a discussion of gaps in knowledge, especially those critical for policy considerations. Overview of CO₂ capture and storage CO₂ is emitted principally from the burning of fossil fuels, both in large combustion units such as those used for electric power generation and in smaller, distributed sources such as automobile engines and furnaces used in residential and commercial buildings. CO₂ emissions also result from some industrial and resource extraction processes, as well as from the burning of forests during land clearance. CCS would most likely be applied to large point sources of CO₂, such as power plants or large industrial processes. Some of these sources could supply decarbonized fuel such as hydrogen to the transportation, industrial, and building sectors and thus reduce emissions from those distributed sources. CCS involves using technology to collect and concentrate the CO₂ produced in industrial and energy-related sources, transport it to a suitable storage location, and then store it away from the atmosphere for a long period. CCS would thus allow fossil fuels to be used with low the proportion of emissions. In 2007, China's power generation industry emitted about 2.8 billion tons of carbon dioxide. A medium-scale (400-600 MW) coal-fired power plant emits millions of tons of carbon dioxide each year. The power generation industry has the characteristics of high energy consumption, large and concentrated carbon dioxide emissions. Compared with the carbon dioxide emitted by automobile exhaust and residents' lives, this fixed-source, large-volume, and concentrated carbon dioxide emission method is easier to treat in a unified manner. Worldwide, the power generation industry is the main field of CCS technology application. The comprehensive utilization of coal is another important area of CCS application. China is a coal-rich country. The development of CCS in China should first consider the combination with the use of coal. In the whole life cycle of coal mining and utilization, coal-fired power plants will release carbon dioxide and carbon dioxide and coal-bed methane (the main component is methane gas, and its greenhouse effect is 21 times that of carbon dioxide). Generally, these processes will produce by-product carbon dioxide in high concentrations. The energy required to capture it will be lower than the capture of carbon dioxide from coal-fired power plants. Therefore, if the entire life cycle from coal mining to comprehensive coal utilization can be cleaned, it is more in line with China's national conditions than simply capturing the carbon dioxide produced by coal combustion.

Carbon capture

CO₂ capture is most likely to be most effective in stationary sources, such as large fossil fuel facilities or bioenergy facilities, industries with major CO₂ emissions, natural gas processing, industrial fuel stations, and fossil fuels based on hydrogen production from plants. CO₂ concentration drops sharply the faster it moves away from the source. A lower concentration increases the mass flow that must be treated (per ton of CO₂ extracted). Air also contains oxygen, but purifying CO₂ from the atmosphere and storing CO₂, can slow down the oxygen cycle. CO₂ is concentrated from coal combustion in relatively pure oxygen and can be processed directly. However, impurities in CO₂ streams can have a significant impact on their phase behavior. They can pose a significant threat to further corrosion of pipelines and well materials. A purification process will be required in cases where CO₂ impurities are present, especially with air retention. Organisms that produce ethanol by fermentation produce essentially pure CO₂ that can be pumped underground. Three different types of technologies for refining processes exist: post-combustion, pre-combustion, and combustion I: Post-combustion: CO₂ is removed after fossil fuel combustion - this is the scheme that will apply to fossil fuels burning the proportion of emissions. In 2007, China's power generation industry emitted about 2.8 billion tons of carbon dioxide. A medium-scale (400-600 MW) coal-fired power plant emits millions of tons of carbon dioxide each year. The power generation industry has the characteristics of high energy consumption, large and concentrated carbon dioxide emissions. Compared with the carbon dioxide emitted by automobile exhaust and residents' lives, this fixed-source, large-volume, and concentrated carbon dioxide emission method is easier to treat in a unified manner. Worldwide, the power generation industry is the main field of CCS technology application. The comprehensive utilization of coal is another important area of CCS application. China is a coal-rich country. The development of CCS

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Power plants. Here, carbon dioxide is captured from the flue gases in power plants or other large stationary sources. The technology is well understood and is currently used in other industrial applications, although not at the same level as would be required in a power plant on a commercial scale.

The technology is widely applied to pre-combustion in fertilizers, chemicals, gaseous fuels (H_2 , CH_4), and energy production. In these cases, the fossil fuel is partially oxidized, for example, in gasification. The resulting increased gas (CO and H_2O) is displaced into more CO_2 and H_2 . The CO_2 generated by the waste stream can be captured relatively pure. H_2 can now be used as a fuel, and the carbon dioxide is removed before combustion. There are many advantages and disadvantages compared to traditional methods of capturing the combustion of carbon dioxide. CO_2 is removed after fossil fuels are burned but before the flue gases are expanded to atmospheric pressure. This scheme is applied to new burning and fossil fuel power plants or existing plants where re-engine is an option. Carrying out CO_2 capture before expansion, i.e., from compressed gas, is standard in almost all industrial CO_2 capture operations and at the same level needed for utility power plants. In the fuel combustion phase, the fuel is burned in oxygen instead of air. TO Reducing the resulting flame temperature to common levels during conventional combustion, the flue gas is circulated and injected into the combustion chamber. The flue gas consists mainly of carbon dioxide and water vapor, the latter of which is condensed through cooling. The result is an almost pure Carbon dioxide stream that can be transported to a site of capture and storage. Power plant and oxyfuel-based combustion processes are sometimes called "zero emissions" cycles because the stored CO_2 is not partly removed from the flue gas stream (as in pre- and post-combustion carbon capture) but the flue gas stream itself. A certain part of the CO_2 generated during combustion processes inevitably ends up in condensed water. Justify the "zero emissions" designation, and the water would have to be treated or disposed of appropriately. A promising technique, but the initial air separation step requires much energy. An alternative method that is under development is chemical combustion loops (CLC). Chemical rings use metal oxide as a solid oxygen carrier. Metal oxide particles react with solid, liquid, or gaseous fuels in fluidized-bed combustion, producing solid metal particles, a mixture of carbon dioxide, and water vapor. The water vapor is condensed, leaving pure carbon dioxide gas, and then it can be isolated. These solid metal particles are circulated to another fluidized bed. They react with air, producing heat and regenerating metal oxide particles circulated to combustion fluidized fluids. A variant of chemical rings is calcium rings, which use alternating carbonate and then calcine from a calcium-based oxide carrier as a means of CO_2 capture. Few engineering proposals have made this task more difficult than capturing CO_2 directly from the atmosphere. However, work in this area is still in its infancy. Detention costs are estimated to be higher than at the source. However, it may be possible to deal with emissions from diffuse sources such as the automobile and aircraft industries. The energy required in theory to capture air is only slightly more than capturing it from its sources. The additional costs come from devices that use natural airflow. Pre-prototype global research techniques demonstrated air capture in 2007. Removing CO_2 from the atmosphere is a form of Geoenvironmental engineering forms by creating greenhouse gases. Techniques of this kind receive widespread media coverage because they promise a comprehensive solution to global warming if effective carbon sequestration technologies can be combined. It is usual to see such techniques proposed

for capturing air, for treatment of flue gases. It is more commonly suggested that carbon dioxide capture and storage in coal-burning plants is in oxygen extracted from the air, which means CO₂ is highly concentrated and no scrubbing process is necessary. According to the Wallowa Energy Resources Center in Washington, it is possible to capture about 65% of the carbon dioxide embedded in it and sequester it into a solid form by gasifying coal.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of possible CCS systems showing the sources for which CCS might be relevant, transport of CO₂, and storage options (courtesy of CO₂CRC) enhanced oil recovery.

Transfer of carbon dioxide before storage

After capture, CO₂ must be transferred to appropriate storage sites. It is done by pipeline, which is usually the cheapest method of transportation. In 2008, approximately 5,800 km of CO₂ pipelines in the United States were used to transport CO₂ to oil production fields. It is then injected into older fields to extract the oil.

The injection of CO₂ to produce oil is commonly called In addition, there are several pilot programs at various stages to test the long-term storage of CO₂ in non-oil-producing geological formations. According to the Congressional Research Service, "there are important unanswered questions about pipeline requirements, economic regulation, benefit to cost recovery, the regulatory classification of CO₂ itself, and pipeline integrity. Moreover, because CO₂ pipelines for EOR are already in use today, policy decisions affecting CO₂ pipelines take on an urgency that is not recognized by many. Federal classification of CO₂ as both a commodity (by the Bureau of Land Management) and as a pollutant (by the Environmental Protection Agency) can lead to potential immediate conflict which may need to be addressed, not only for the sake of future CCS implementation but also to ensure consistency of future CCS with today's CO₂ pipeline operations." A COA conveyor belt system or vessel can also be used for transportation. These methods are currently being used to transport CO₂ for other applications.

Carbon dioxide sequestration

Various forms of permanent CO₂ storage have been conceptualized. These forms include gaseous storage in various deep geological formations (including salt formations and gas fields), liquid storage in the ocean, and solid storage by reacting CO₂ with metal oxides to produce stable carbonate.

- Storage in the geological layers of the Earth

Also known as geological confinement, this method involves injecting CO₂ directly into underground geological formations. Oil fields, gas fields, brine formations, unmakeable coal seams, and saline-filled basalt formations have been proposed as storage sites. Various appropriate physical (egg, highly impermeable shale) and geochemical mechanisms will prevent CO₂ from escaping to the surface. Sometimes CO₂ is injected into oil fields to decrease oil recovery rates. About 30 to 50 million metric tons of CO₂ per year in the United States are injected into declining oil fields. This option is attractive because the geology of oil and gas reservoirs is usually well understood, and storage costs can be partially offset by the sale of additional oil that is recovered. Disadvantages of old oil fields and their geographical distribution and limited capacity, and the subsequent burning of additional oil extracted for it will make up for much or all reduction in CO₂ emissions. Unmakeable coal seams can be used to store CO₂ because CO₂ particles attach to the surface of the coal. Technical feasibility, however, depends on the permeability of the coal bed. In adsorption releases previously absorbed coal and methane, methane can be recovered (from coal recovery promotion). It could be used to sell methane to offset part of the cost of storing CO₂. However, burning the resulting methane produces CO₂, which would cancel out some benefits of sequestering the original CO₂. Salt formations contain highly mineralized saline, and so far, they have been considered of no benefit to humans. In a few cases, saline

Figure 2. Schematic showing carbon dioxide sequestration.

1. Carbon dioxide storage in the Earth's geological layers:

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been used to store chemical waste. The main advantage of saline aquifers is the huge volume of potential storage and their common occurrence. The main disadvantage of saline aquifers is that relatively little is known about them, especially compared to oil fields. They maintain an acceptable storage cost, which may be limited in geophysical exploration, which results in an atmosphere of uncertainty about the structure of the aquifer. Unlike storage in oil or coal fields, The product will not offset storage costs. CO₂ leakage back into the atmosphere may be a problem in saline groundwater storage. However, existing research shows that several appropriate mechanisms immobilize underground CO₂, reducing the risk of leakage. Lichen Mokhtar, the design and management of geological storage sites, estimates CO₂ could be trapped for millions of years. The sites are likely to retain more than 99% of the CO₂ injected over 1,000 years. In 2009 it was reported that scientists had mapped 6,000 square miles (16,000 km²) of rock formations in the United States that could be used to store up to 500 years of US carbon dioxide emissions. Storage of CO₂ in deep, onshore, or offshore geological formations uses many of the same technologies that have been developed by the oil and gas industry and have been proven to be economically feasible under specific conditions for oil and gas fields and saline formations, but not yet for storage in unmixable coal beds⁸ (see Figure SPM.4).

Figure 3. Overview of geological storage options (based on Figure 4 (Courtesy CO₂CRC)).

2.Ocean Storage of CO₂:

Another proposed form of carbon storage is in the oceans. Several concepts have been proposed: CO₂ injects "dissolution" by ships or pipelines into the ocean water column at a depth of 1000-3000 m, upward cloud formation, and CO₂ subsequently dissolves into seawater. Through the "lake" deposits, by injecting CO₂ directly into the sea at a depth greater than 3000 meters, where the high pressure liquefies the CO₂, making it denser than water, and forming a low cloud, which may accumulate at the bottom of the sea and the lake." Expected to delay the dissolution of CO₂ in the oceans and atmosphere, possibly for thousands of years. Use a chemical reaction to combine CO₂ with a carbonate mineral (such as limestone) to form bicarbonate(s), for example, $CO_2 + CaCO_3 + H_2O \rightarrow Calcium (HCO_3)_2 (AQ)$. However, the aqueous bicarbonate solution must not be allowed to dry out, or else the reaction will reverse.CO₂ storage in solid hydrate hydrates already on the ocean floor or a more solid buckle growing. The environmental effects of oceanic storage are negative in general. It is not understood. Large concentrations of CO₂ can kill living organisms in the ocean. However, another problem is that the dissolved CO₂ eventually has to equilibrate with the atmosphere, so the storage will not be permanent. In addition, as part of CO₂ Reacts with water to form carbonic acid, H₂CO₃, the acidity of ocean water increases. The mystery remains shrouds the ecological implications of the benthic life-forms of the bathypelagic, abyssopelagic, and hadopelagic regions. Although life is rather sparse in the deep ocean basins, the energy and chemicals in the effects of these deep basins can have far-reaching effects. Much more needs to be done to

determine the extent of potential problems. The time it takes for water in the deep ocean to circulate to the surface has been estimated to be approximately 1,600 years, depending on currents and other changing conditions. The cost of removing liquid CO₂ from the deep ocean is estimated at US\$40-80/ton of CO₂ (2002\$). This figure covers the costs of guarding at the power plant and shipping to the waste disposal site. The bicarbonate approach would reduce acidity and enhance CO₂ retention in the ocean, increasing costs and other environmental impacts. An additional method of long-term ocean-based confinement is to collect crop residues such as corn stalks or straw into bales likely to significantly increase biomass and deposit them in sedimentary fans areas of the deep ocean basin. Dropping this waste into alluvial fans causes the waste to be buried quickly in silt on the seafloor, sequestering biomass for very long periods. Placer fans are found in all oceans and seas of the world. They are located off the delta of the river edge of the continental shelf, such as the Mississippi Alluvial Fan in the Gulf of Mexico and the Fan of the Mississippi Alluvium in the Gulf of Mexico. Alluvial Nile in the Mediterranean. Unfortunately, biomass and crop residues constitute a very important and valuable component of topsoil agriculture and sustainable development. Taking it out of the terrestrial equation is fraught with risks and problems. [citation needed] If pollinated crops are used, it exacerbates nutrient depletion, increasing dependence on chemical fertilizers and, therefore, petrochemicals, thus defeating original intentions to reduce atmospheric CO₂. However, it is more likely to use less expensive energy crops than cellulose. These are usually unfertilized, although it is likely that petrochemicals can still be used for assembly and transportation.

Figure 4. Overview of ocean storage concepts. In "dissolution type" ocean storage, the CO₂ rapidly dissolves in the ocean water, whereas in "lake type" ocean storage, the CO₂ is initially a liquid on the seafloor (Courtesy CO₂CRC).

Some ocean scientists are advocating for storing captured CO₂ emissions in the deep ocean. The reasons why might surprise. This study will investigate why some think ocean storage of CO₂ is a good idea and the potential impacts on the marine environment.

How to Stop Climate Change: Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a naturally occurring gas that plants and algae rely on for photosynthesis. We rely on them for the oxygen we breathe. Since the Industrial Revolution, we have been ejecting increasingly larger amounts of CO₂ into the atmosphere, leading to a warmer planet and ocean acidification.

If we want to mitigate climate change, a straightforward solution is reducing carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. One strategy to rapidly decarbonize and reduce CO₂ emissions is adopting renewable energy and improved energy efficiency, but this is not enough. Even if we somehow managed to stop emitting CO₂ today magically, there is still a

tremendous amount in the atmosphere that will contribute to climate change for centuries to come. In addition to decarbonization, we need to remove excess CO₂ from the atmosphere.

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Carbon Capture and Storage: Our planet has natural carbon sinks that do this already: terrestrial plants, soil, and marine algae, for example. The oceans are one of the largest sinks on the planet, absorbing roughly 25 percent of the atmospheric CO₂ we emit each year. However, these natural processes take time and cannot keep up with our current level of emissions. Evidence of this fact is in the numbers: global atmospheric CO₂ concentration in 1960 was 317 parts per million (ppm), by 1990 was 354 ppm, by 2010 it was 390 ppm, and today it is 408 ppm.

CO₂ during ice ages and warm periods for the past 800,000 years

Figure 5. Atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are at their highest levels ever. Source: NOAA Climate.gov

Nature needs help. We need to pull CO₂ out of the atmosphere and store it away. This idea of capturing CO₂ from the air and then transporting and storing it in a manufactured 'sink' separated from the atmosphere is called carbon capture and sequestration (or storage), known as CCS. Many different tools and methods are being researched to capture and transport Carbon. However, will not focus on those here. Want to focus on CO₂ sequestration in this post, not in tanks or underground, but in the ocean.

Ocean Storage of CO₂ It seems counter-intuitive: the oceans are turning more acidic due to too much CO₂, and we want to put more CO₂ in there? It is a controversial idea, but some think that it makes logical sense. To be clear, this is not a solution to climate change but perhaps a way to avoid the worst of it. Let us take a look.

Storage is required to isolate captured CO₂ from the atmosphere. Traditional storage techniques trap captured CO₂ as a liquid or gas deep injection hole and prevent release. With ocean storage of CO₂, the gas is intentionally injected into the deep ocean and is either allowed to the underground in specific geological features (such as abandoned hydrocarbon wells) and require a non-porous plug to seal the diffuse or be trapped in a specific location, depending on the depth and pressure.

Three general methods could be used to inject carbon dioxide into the ocean for storage directly. First would be a pipe that runs from shore to the ocean depths. This pipe would receive a stream of carbon dioxide from capture or intermediary storage facility on the coast and then direct it offshore for long-term storage.

In the dispersal by ship method, CO₂ stored onboard the vessel would be ejected at great depths using a long hose or pipe towed behind the vessel, promoting rapid diffusion of the CO₂ into seawater. The third method would be to use a stationary vessel or platform to inject CO₂ to a fixed location at or near the ocean bottom.

Figure 6. for ocean storage of CO₂. Source: IPCC (Artwork courtesy Sean Goddard, University of Exeter)

Carbon dioxide storage in metals:

In this process, CO₂ is exothermically reacted with available metal oxides, producing stable carbonates. This process occurs naturally over many years and is responsible for much of the surface limestone. The idea of using olivine was popularized by Schilling, a professor of chemistry and geology. The reaction rate can be made faster, for example, by responding to higher temperatures or pressures or by pretreatment of metals. However, this method can require additional energy. The IPCC estimates that a power plant equipped with CCS using mineral storage energy need 60-180% more than a power plant without CCS. Furthermore, the economics of mineral carbonation on a large scale is being tested in the world's first pilot plant project based in Newcastle, Australia. The Greengage Group and the University of Newcastle developed new mineral activation and reaction techniques, with funding from the New South Wales and Australian governments to be ready by 2013. A study on mineral sequestration in the United States: Carbon sequestration by reaction of naturally occurring magnesium and calcium-containing minerals with CO₂ carbonate formation has many unique advantages. Most notable[e] is that there is a lower energy carbonate state than CO₂, which is why thermal unfavorable mineral carbonation occurs naturally (egg, weathering of rocks over geological timescales). Secondly, raw materials such as magnesium-based minerals are abundant. Finally, carbonate production is undoubtedly stable, and thus re-release of CO₂ into the atmosphere is not an issue. However, conventional carbonate pathways remain slow under ambient temperatures and pressures. The major challenge addressed by these efforts is to identify a synthetically and environmentally viable carbonate pathway that would allow for mineral uptake to be implemented with a good economy.

4.3. Storage in metal-carbon dioxide:

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Carbon leak

The main concern is whether CCS with a leak of stored carbon dioxide will compromise CCS as a climate change mitigation option. The IPCC estimates that risks are similar to those associated with current oil and gas activity for their well-chosen design and management of geological storage sites. Although some question this as an arbitrary assumption noting the lack of experience in storing these in the long term. Furthermore, although some seepage occurs upward through the soil, the storage sites are well located and likely to retain more than 99% of the CO₂ injection over 1000 years. Leakage through the injection tube is the greatest danger. Although injection tubes are usually protected with no return valves to prevent power outages, there is still a risk that the tube itself could rupture and leak due to compression. For example, a modest release of carbon dioxide from a pipeline under a bridge resulted in the death of some ducks there. In order to measure accidental carbon emissions more accurately and reduce the risk of fatalities through this type of leakage, it has been proposed to implement a carbon dioxide alert meter around the perimeter of the project. In 1986 a large leak of naturally isolated carbon dioxide from Lake Neos in Cameroon rose and suffocated 1,700 people. While the Carbon was sequestered naturally, some suggest this event is evidence of the potentially catastrophic effects of artificially sequestering Carbon. The Lake Neos catastrophe resulted from a volcanic event, which released very suddenly as much as a cubic amount of carbon dioxide gas out of a pool of naturally occurring carbon dioxide under the lake in a deep ravine. This pool of carbon dioxide is not a place where humans can inject or store carbon dioxide. This pool is not known about nor monitored until after natural disasters. For ocean storage, carbon dioxide retention depends on depth. IgG estimates 30-85% of the captured carbon dioxide will be retained after 500 years to depths 1000-3000 m. Mineral storage is not considered as having any risks of leakage. The IPCC recommends setting limits on the amount of leakage that can occur. May rule out deep ocean storage as an option. It should be noted that in the conditions of the deepest oceans (about 400 bar or 40 MPa, 280 K) (where carbonate formation/acidification is the rate-limiting step), but the formation of CO₂ from water hydrates, a type of hard water cage that surrounds the CO₂ Carbon, unfavorable. Available geological information shows the absence of major tectonic events after the [brine reservoir] dislocation. That is means that the geological environment is stable and a suitable location for carbon dioxide storage. The solubility of trapping is the most durable and safe form of geological storage.

CO₂ Recycling / Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU)

Recycling carbon dioxide may respond to the global challenge of significantly reducing GHG emissions from major (industrial) static emitters in the near and medium-term. However, it is typically considered a different technological class than CCS. Technologies under development, such as CCS bio-algae synthesis, use a CO₂ pre-chimney (such as

from a coal-fired power plant) as a useful input feedstock for oil-rich algae production in solar membranes for oil production for plastics, transportation fuels (including jet fuel), and as a stock feeder Feed for farm animal production. CO₂ and other captured greenhouse gases are injected into membranes containing sewage and identify strains of algae causing, combined with sunlight or ultraviolet light, the oil-rich biomass to double in mass every 24 hours. The biosynthesis of algae photosynthesis is based on the Earth sciences: the technology is completely synthesis and emitting, and capital expenditures can provide a return on investment due to the higher value of the goods produced (for oil, plastics, fuels, and feed). Using storage of pre-emission CO₂ fumes (and other greenhouse gases) as a feedstock in the growth Of oil-rich algae biomass, Queensland, New South Wales is being trialed. CCS biomass testing facilities in Australia's three largest coal-fired power plants, in membranes Enclosed for the production of plastic transportation fuel and nutritious animal feed. Another method that can be useful in dealing with industrial sources of carbon dioxide is to convert it into hydrocarbons, where it can be stored or used as fuel or in the manufacture of plastics. Several projects have investigated this possibility. Existing carbon dioxide purification variants are based on potassium carbonate, which can create liquid fuels. However, this process requires a significant amount of energy input. Although creating fuels from carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is not a geoengineering technique, nor does it work as a greenhouse gas treatment, it could create a low carbon economy. Another use is to produce stable carbonate from silicate (i.e., olivine to produce magnesium carbonate. This process is still in the research and development stage).

1. The first method: methanol

A proven process for oil and gas production is to make methanol. It is not easy to synthesize methanol from carbon dioxide and H₂. Based on this fact, the idea of a methanol economy was born.

2. The second method: oil and gas

In the Department of Industrial Chemistry and Materials Engineering at the University of Messina, Italy, there is a project to develop a system that works like a fuel cell in reverse, using a catalyst that enables sunlight to split water into hydrogen and oxygen ions (through a membrane) where they react with carbon dioxide to produce the material hydrocarbon.

3. Third method

If carbon dioxide is heated to 2400°C, it breaks down into carbon monoxide (CO) and oxygen. The Fischer-tropic process can then be used to convert carbon dioxide into oil and gas. The desired temperature can be achieved using a chamber containing a mirror to focus sunlight on the gas. The teams competing to develop such chambers are at Sandia National Laboratories, both based in New Mexico. According to Sandia, these chambers can provide enough fuel for 100% of the energy of domestic cars using 5,800 square kilometers, biofuels this will not take fertile land away from crops but will be land that is not used for anything else. James Financing through the Clean Development Mechanism:

One way to fund future carbon dioxide capture and storage projects is through the Clean Development Mechanism of the Kyoto Protocol. At the Sixteenth United Nations Climate Change Conference in 2010, the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice, at its thirty-third session, issued a draft document recommending the inclusion of carbon dioxide capture and storage in geological formations in the CDM project activities. At the 17th United Nations Climate Change Conference in Durban, a final agreement was reached to enable carbon dioxide capture and storage projects supported through the Clean Development Mechanism.

Cost

There are many reasons why carbon capture and storage should be expected to cause price increases if it is used in gas-fired power plants. First, increased CCS energy requirements lead to significantly higher operating costs for CCS power plants. Additionally, there are additional costs of investment and capital. This process would increase the fuel requirements of a CCS plant by about 15% for a gas plant. It is estimated that the cost of this additional fuel and storage and other system costs could increase the energy costs of a CCS power plant by 30% to 60%, depending on the particular

circumstances. Pre-commercial CCS demonstration projects are likely to be more expensive than completed CCS technology, with the total incremental costs of a large initial demonstration project estimated to range from €0.5 to €1.1 billion per project over the life of the project. Other applications can be used. CCS technology was tested in coal-fired plants in the early 2000s. However, it was not economically viable in most countries (trials are still underway in China as of 2019 but faces logistical challenges in transportation and storage).

The cost of carbon dioxide capture and storage depends on capture and storage, which varies according to the method used. The cost of geological storage in saline formations or depleted oil or gas fields typically ranges from US\$0.50 to US\$8.00 per ton of CO₂ injected, plus an additional US\$0.10 to US\$0.30 to cover monitoring costs. But when storage is combined with EOR to extract additional oil from an oil field, storage may yield a net benefit of \$10-16 per ton of CO₂ injected (based on 2003 oil prices). That is likely to negate some of the effects of carbon dioxide capture when oil is burned as a fuel.

The cost of electricity generated from various sources, including carbon dioxide capture and storage technologies, can be found in electricity costs by energy source.

If carbon dioxide capture is part of the fuel cycle, carbon dioxide will have value, not cost. The solar or methane fuel cycle put forward by the Fraunhofer Society is, among others, an example of a gas-to-energy system. This "solar fuel" cycle uses; Excess renewable electrical energy for hydrogen formation by electrolysis of water. The hydrogen is then combined with carbon dioxide to create synthetic natural gas and stored in the gas network. However, this system is not a CCS system, as carbon dioxide is released into the atmosphere when methane burns.

In 2018, it was estimated that carbon pricing of at least €100 would be required for industrial CCS technology to be feasible.

According to UK government estimates in the late 2000s, it was estimated that CO₂ capture (without storage) would add £7 per MWh by 2025 to the cost of electricity from a modern gas-fired power plant: but most of the CO₂ would need to be stored Carbon so that the total increase in the cost of generating electricity from gas or biomass is about 50%. Governments worldwide have provided various financial support for CCS pilot projects, including tax credits, allowances, and grants. Funding is linked to the desire to accelerate innovation activities related to CCS as a low carbon technology and the need for economic stimulus activities. As of 2011, approximately \$23.5 billion has been saved to support these large-scale projects worldwide.

Summary and Recommendations

The research discusses the critical role of Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage (CCS) in mitigating climate change, focusing on methods to reduce atmospheric CO₂ levels. It explores various CCS techniques, including storage in geological layers, oceans, and through mineral carbonation. The studies evaluate the effectiveness, costs, and feasibility of these methods, considering their long-term ecological impacts. Recommendations include prioritizing research on efficient and cost-effective CCS methods, ensuring safe storage to minimize environmental risks, and integrating CCS with broader climate change mitigation strategies.

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